

Do Brief Motivational Interventions Reduce Alcohol-impaired Driving Among College Students? A Meta-analysis of Individual Participant Data

“I am unique in my own field (behavioral sciences) in that I set the standard for data/code sharing at a time when no one else was doing it, not because it was a requirement, I did it voluntarily, because I bought into open science. We have a responsibility to the public to leverage the data we already have to accelerate discovery.”

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Datasets and R codes available: <https://data.mendeley.com/datasets/j45wkj23c5/2>

- <https://doi.org/10.17632/h2sd5y6fxp.1>
- <https://doi.org/10.17632/r5bztd766.1>
- <https://doi.org/10.17632/kpjp3gnwbt.1>
- <https://doi.org/10.17632/ndzhdv86dg.1>
- <https://doi.org/10.31234/osf.io/bhkry>
- <https://doi.org/10.17632/97bzg6z28h.1>
- <http://doi.org/10.17632/vnpw693nnd.1>
- <https://doi.org/10.17632/t2yk5kt3bw.1>
- <http://dx.doi.org/10.17632/4dw4kn97fz.2>
- <http://doi.org/10.17632/yf2xkjvd4k.1>
- <http://doi.org/10.17632/j45wkj23c5.1>

Funding: National Institute on Alcohol Abuse and Alcoholism (R01 AA019511, K02 AA028630)

We shared data from Project INTEGRATE, a large-scale research synthesis project combining data from brief intervention trials for alcohol misuse among young adults. The shared dataset exemplifies both data sharing and reuse. It is a data reuse case because we obtained and curated raw data from clinical trials for research synthesis. It is an emerging field in clinical research, which enables robust inference from raw data across multiple clinical trials. What we generated is nonetheless distinct from the original raw data, as we made the data comparable across trials through analytical work. We have long advocated open science. Based on our work, we competed for the inaugural NIH DataWorks! Prize Challenge (NIH Office of Data Science Strategy) in 2022. We were one of the finalist teams that NIH showcased.

Sharing Methodology

The methodological approaches we have developed are applicable to other areas of interest. The computational tools and data generated through our research offer opportunities for further analysis and can support new studies. Transparency and reproducibility are essential, as is accelerating the pace of discovery. Observing and following others' methods and examples can facilitate faster learning and innovation. Access to data remains a crucial component.

Gathering original data, particularly clinical data, requires significant resources. Yet, often only a small portion of this data is used to produce new insights. Data sharing plays a vital role in generating clinical knowledge, and its importance cannot be overstated in the current era of data science and artificial intelligence.

Our research has clarified the effectiveness and duration of brief alcohol interventions for young adults, a topic previously marked by controversial conclusions. We believe our research has addressed this question thoroughly through multiple analyses. Future studies can examine intervention effects at the individual level. Establishing whether brief alcohol interventions are effective overall was an important first step; attention can now shift to individual-level predictions.

We have also shared data and computing codes on arXiv and PsyArXiv (Open Science Framework). However, we have used Mendeley Data more frequently. They are all relatively easy to navigate.

Impact

Our work is built on open science principles. It is critical that we follow through and set good examples. We made a YouTube video at [UNT Health: Project INTEGRATE](https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=35eWFfifXLw).

The data sets we shared have been used as application examples for a new method or as training data for machine learning algorithms. For example, for [Data and code for: A tutorial on individual participant data meta-analysis using Bayesian multilevel modeling to estimate alcohol intervention effects across heterogeneous studies \(2019\)](https://academic.oup.com/alcalc/article/57/1/125/6137891) - [Mendeley Data](https://academic.oup.com/alcalc/article/57/1/125/6137891), we have at least one paper that used the data set in a new publication titled, [Relative Efficiency of Using Summary Versus Individual Data in Random-Effects Meta-Analysis | Biometrics | Oxford Academic](https://academic.oup.com/alcalc/article/57/1/125/6137891).

Our work has extended to training the next generation on machine learning and applied artificial intelligence using existing data (R25 DA061742).

